

THE IMPACT OF PARENTAL DISHARMONY ON SELF-ESTEEM, AND SOCIAL SKILLS OF ADOLESCENTS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between Parental Disharmony, Self-Esteem and Social Skills in adolescents between the ages of 12 and 18. Cross-sectional Correlational Research Design was used with a sample of 210 adolescents from public schools with equal proportion of gender, boys (N=105) and girls (N=105). Data were collected using standardized tools: Parental Disharmony Scale (PDS; Amjad & Saleem, 2014), Self-Esteem Scale for Adolescents (SES; Saleem & Mahmood, 2011), and Interpersonal Skills Scale (IPSS; Zahra et al., 2020). Relationship between the study variables were found using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Linear Regression was also conducted to determine the significant predictors of Interpersonal Skills. Results revealed that Parental Disharmony has significant negative relationship with Self-Esteem and Social Skills ($p > .001$). In contrast, there was a strong positive relationship between Self-Esteem and Social Skills ($p > .001$). Furthermore, gender ($p > .05$) and Self-Esteem factors ($p > .01$) ($p > .05$) were significant positive predictors of Interpersonal Skills. This study illustrated the relevance of cultural context and provide compelling evidence of how Parental Disharmony can adversely affect adolescence Self-Esteem and Social Skills. It was recommended that further studies be conducted to validate and expand these findings, to ensure their applicability to a wider population.

Keywords: Parental Disharmony, Self-Esteem, Social Skills, Interpersonal Skills, Adolescents

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a complex stage of human development between childhood and adulthood from 13 to 19 years (Coleman, 2022). This phase involves significant biopsychosocial and social changes, typically biological changes such as growth in height, weight, and secondary sexual characteristics, alongside psychosocial changes including the

development of reasoning skills, self-identity, self-esteem, and social skills. These developmental processes are influenced by individual traits and their environment (Irfan et al., 2024). Teenagers often face peer pressure, academic challenges and family-related issues during this stage. One of the most common issues is self-esteem-building during which, self-

worth fluctuates and the individual becomes sensitive to external validation from peers and society (Rizvi et al., 2024). This leads to diminished confidence while social interactions and decision-making abilities are compromised greatly (de Vries, 2020). This phenomenon was explained by Erickson in his theory of Psychosocial Developmental Stages, where "Identity Vs. Role Confusion" was a stage of adolescence in which individual develops self-worth based on his environment and if that environment is unsupportive, then the adolescent undergoes confusion state leading to loosening of self-worth (Orenstein & Lewis, 2022).

The development of self-esteem is related to factors like peer interactions, academic success and family dynamics (Adnan et al., 2024). Families are essential in shaping society and culture, especially in collectivistic cultures like Pakistan (Mumtaz et al., 2023, Saleem, et al., 2019). Although, parents are the crucial part of family in any culture as, they provide the children with primary care (Rajpoot & Chaudhry, 2020). With the progression of an individual's development, his parents' relationship also progresses and certain conflicts are bound to arise. Thus, parental disharmony is defined as disagreement or argument between parents that could result in lesser or greater interaction between the parents (Syehan et al., 2023). Worldwide teenagers are seen to blame themselves for the disharmony among parents without knowing the major factors behind it (Branje et al., 2021). Also, the social cognitive theory based on the modelling concept by Bandura, highlighted that adolescents learn certain behaviors by observing their caregivers (Abbas et al., 2025). When parents have conflicts, adolescents develop maladaptive beliefs about themselves and their overall skills (Nunes & Faro, 2021).

According to a systematic review on family development, the main causes for parental disharmony were financial issues, individual characteristics, changes in growth and development, increasing family size and needs, poverty, interference by in-laws, domestic duties, conflict due to wives' careers, and refusal of the wife to give authority to the husband (Maksymova et al., 2021). Recently, parental disharmony has been distinguished into two

categories; constructive and destructive. Constructive conflicts lower the likelihood of teenager's involvement in violent activities and leads to healthy coping abilities and problem-solving strategies in them. While, destructive conflicts develop emotional insecurity, hopelessness, anxiety, and worry that leads to the risk of occurring internalizing disorders and externalizing disorders like lack of control, anger, aggressive tendencies and worsening of their self-esteem (Warmuth et al., 2020). One of the pioneers in the field of psychology, Rosenberg claimed that self-esteem relates to a person's overall positive evaluation of himself or herself. According to the previous studies, self-esteem entails two components, first is the belief that one is competent and trust their capacity to reason and the second one is the belief that one has the right to happiness and fulfilment that comes in their lives (Casale, 2020). While, low self-esteem in adolescence predicted a high risk of mental health problems, substance abuse, and less satisfaction with relationships in adulthood, it also affected the social skills of the individual (Szcześniak et al., 2022).

In addition, American Psychological Association (2013) defined social skills as a set of learned abilities that allow an individual to interact appropriately in a particular social context. Gresham described three kinds of social skills i.e., peer acceptance, behavioral, and social validity. Leary's Sociometer theory interpreted that self-esteem acts as a barometer of social acceptance; therefore, low self-esteem teenagers perceive themselves to be worthless and not able to interact socially. This resulted in struggles with assertiveness, anxiety in social interactions and withdrawal from engaging in social opportunities in educational settings (Yu et al., 2024). This cycle becomes self-reinforcing and isolates the adolescents from meaningful peer interactions and develops a sense of inadequacy in them (Shoaib, 2022).

Moreover, Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs explained that the highest state of self-actualization is achieved if basic physical needs are met, a person feels safe in his environment, creates a sense of belongingness within relationships and develops a high self-esteem. When family support is lacking, individuals are not able to move to the next stage which is

building of self-esteem leading to low academic performance, adjustment problems, low self-esteem, and poor social skills. Family interactions provide significant social influence and connections throughout life and manage strain by providing love, guidance, and a sense of purpose (Cherry 2022; Christenson & Reschly, 2010). Also, gender differences were also observed in Pakistani context as, gender roles and norm of both gender in adolescence period undergo a shifting stage and the teenagers are expected to become smart and mature over-night (Mihalec-Adkins & Cooley, 2020). Pakistani culture is more traditional than the western culture. The girls are entitled to be modest, obedient and socially conforming under restrictive expectations. This conditioning leads them to low self-esteem and discouragement from pursuing goals (Mahmood & Butt, 2022). On the other hand, boys are more freedom-oriented and take leadership roles in the patriarchal society. Being masculine and breadwinners of the family, the boys get responsibilities that tend to stress them. The failure to meet these expectations related to masculinity establishes worthlessness and isolation from social activities (Naeem et al., 2023).

Hence, the literature revealed that there is a significant association among parental disharmony, low-self-esteem and poor social skills. The current research is aimed at determining the relationship among these three constructs of an adolescent's life by predicting the factors that can cause contradiction of interpersonal skills specifically in Pakistani culture. The reason for this particular combination is it has never been explored with respect to interpersonal skills of an individual in this culture.

Objectives

- To determine the relationship among Parental Disharmony, Self-Esteem, and Social Skills in Adolescents.
- To investigate how Parental Disharmony factors influences different dimensions of Self-Esteem and Social Skills in Adolescents.
- To find out the predictors of Interpersonal Skills in Adolescents.

Hypotheses

- **H1:** It is hypothesized that Parental Disharmony would be significantly negatively

associated with Self-Esteem and Social Skills in Adolescents.

- **H2:** It is hypothesized that there would be a significant positive association between Self-Esteem and Social Skills in adolescents.

- **H3:** It is hypothesized that Parental Disharmony and Self-Esteem would be significant predictors of Interpersonal Skills in Adolescence.

METHOD

Research Design

The Cross-sectional Correlational research design of the survey method was used in this study.

Participants

A sample of participants, 210 were selected by using non-probability purposive sampling, including 105 boys and 105 girls from different government schools in Lahore. The participants of the 8th (33.30%) 9th (33.30%) and 10th (33.30%) classes were targeted with the age range of 12-18 years ($M=14.64$, $SD=1.19$).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The study focused on Adolescence of 8th, 9th and 10th class from government schools. Participants having any sensory or physical disability were excluded and individuals with only one parent were excluded.

Measures

Demographic Performa. A demographic questionnaire was developed based on the literature that was used in the study. Only demographic variables were included that have an association with parental disharmony. These variables include age, gender, family system, and education of parents.

Parental Disharmony Scale (PDS; Amjad & Saleem, 2014). This scale was developed indigenously in Pakistan. It comprised of 27 items that include three dimensions i.e., lack of understanding, financial issues and lack of trust in adolescents from age 12-18, and the scale ranges from 0(never), 1(sometimes), 2(often), 3(always). The reliability of this scale is .87.

Self-Esteem Scale for Adolescents (SES; Saleem & Mahmood, 2011). The self-esteem scale is a self-report tool designed for adolescents, consisting of 44 items rated on a 5-point scale: 0 (not at all), 1 (rarely), 2 (to some extent), 3 (very much), and 4 (always). Scores were calculated by summing the individual item scores, with total scores ranging from 0-176.

The scale is divided into four domains containing three positive and one negative. Positive domains include academic self-esteem, self-confidence, social self-esteem, and negative one named as low self-esteem. .72 is the reliability of this scale.

Interpersonal Skills Scale (IPSS; Zahra et al., 2020). The interpersonal skills scale was established in Pakistan according to our culture to measure the three dimensions of interpersonal skills of adolescents which include social engagement, sociability, and social etiquette. It has 36 items based on a 5-point rating scale ranging from 0 (not at all), 1 (rarely), 2 (to some extent), 3 (very much), and 4 (always). Scores of this scale are computed by adding each item score to the scale. A higher score implies better interpersonal abilities with values ranging from 0 to 172 being possible. This scale has .81 reliability.

Procedure

First of all, schools were contacted and a brief description of the research aims was explained to them. After the permission, the schools participating in the research were visited by the researcher. Institutes and participants were assured about the confidentiality that their information was not shared with any person and only used for research purposes. Firstly, an introduction was given to the participants. Participants were informed about the research aims, and objectives and assured the participants that no answer was right or wrong. They were asked to encircle a response that was closely related to them. The participants who were willing to participate were included. A total of 105 boys and 105 girls were targeted from 10 different schools. All the instructions were given in the Urdu language. There was no limit imposed on the students to fill out the questionnaire. In the end, after the analysis of all the data collected, the students, their teachers, and the school administration received a debriefing session from the research team.

Ethical Considerations

Firstly, the research aims and objectives were explained to the Ethical Review Board, they did a cost and benefit analysis, passed the research that was safe for the community, and no harm was caused to the participants or community. Then, informed consent was

obtained from the participants before conducting the survey which includes all the necessary information the participants should know including the act that their results will be kept confidential and no harm will be made to participants or any other person during the research process. The researcher debriefed the results and related information to the participants at the end.

RESULTS

Frequency and Percentage

Table 1 depicted that the current study sample consisted of 210 participants. Boys and girls each constituted 50% of the total sample. It also indicated that classes 8th, 9th, and 10th comprised 33.3% respectively. Most participants belong to the nuclear family system constituting 74.8% as compared to the joint family system. Moreover, most of the father's education was Matric (28.6%). Similarly, the mother's higher education of the participants was also Matric (29%).

Normality

Normality Analysis was conducted to check the normal distribution of data. The findings indicated that mean and 5% trimmed mean are almost equal, both the values of skewness (.33) and kurtosis (.58) are within -3 to +3 range, fulfilling all the assumptions of normality and confirming that the data was normally distributed and suitable for parametric analysis (see Table 2).

Correlation

Table 3 showed the inter-factor Correlational Analysis. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to find out the relationship between Parental Disharmony, Self-Esteem, and Interpersonal Skills in adolescents. There was a highly negative significant relationship between Lack of Understanding between parents and the Academic Self-Esteem, Self-Confidence, and Social Self-Esteem of the participant. There was a positive relationship between a Lack of Understanding between parents and Low Self-Esteem. Furthermore, a Lack of Understanding between parents was highly negatively significantly associated with Social Engagement. Financial Issues, which is a factor of Parental Disharmony, have a highly negative and significant relationship with the Academic Self-Esteem, Social Self-Esteem, and Social Engagement of the participants. Similarly, the

Financial Issues of parents were positively associated with the Low Self-Esteem of the participants. Lack of Trust between parents has highly negatively significantly associated with Self-Confidence, Social Self-Esteem, and Social Engagement. Lack of Trust between parents has a negative significant relationship between Academic Self-Esteem and Social Etiquette. There was a positive relationship between Lack of Trust and Low Self-Esteem of participants. Moreover, Academic Self-Esteem was significantly positively associated with Social Engagement and Social Etiquette. Self-Confidence was highly significant and positively associated with all three factors of Interpersonal Skills i.e., Social Engagement, Sociability, and Social Etiquette. Social Self-Esteem has a highly positive significant relationship between Social Engagement and Social Etiquette and was positively associated with Sociability. Low Self-Esteem has a significant negative relationship with Social Engagement and a positive relationship with Sociability. Together, these findings suggested that Parental Disharmony has significant negative relationship with Self-Esteem and Interpersonal Skills, having higher Parental Disharmony was associated with lower Self-Esteem and poor Interpersonal Skills. Self-Esteem and Interpersonal Skills have significant positive relationship, indicating higher Self-Esteem was associated with better Interpersonal Skills.

Linear Regression

Linear Regression Analysis was conducted to find out the predictors of Interpersonal Skills. Findings depicted that age, gender, family system, Parental Disharmony, and Self-Esteem jointly explain 44% variance in Interpersonal Skills. These results suggested that gender and Self-Esteem were significant predictors of Interpersonal Skills. Gender and Self-Esteem (Self-Confidence & Social Self-Esteem) act as positive predictors of Interpersonal Skills. Having a higher level of Self-Esteem and being female gender was associated significantly with higher Interpersonal Skills. However, age, class, family system, and factors of Parental Disharmony were not significant predictors of Interpersonal Skills (see Table 4).

Table 1

Frequencies and Percentages of Demographic Characteristics of the Participants (N = 210)

Variables	f	%
Gender		
Boys	105	50
Girls	105	50
Class		
8 th	70	33.3
9 th	70	33.3
10 th	70	33.3
Family System		
Nuclear	157	74.8
Joint	53	25.2
Father's Education		
Illiterate	29	13.8
Under Matric	38	18.1
Matric	60	28.6
Intermediate	30	14.3
Graduation	33	15.7
MS/MA	16	7.6
MPhil	2	1
PhD	2	1
Mother's Education		
Illiterate	36	17.1
Under Matric	39	18.6
Matric	61	29.0
Intermediate	37	17.6
Graduation	17	8.1
MS/MA	17	8.1
MPhil	2	1
PhD	1	.5

Note. f= frequency, %= percentage of participants

Table 2

Normality of Parental Disharmony Scale, Self-Esteem Scale, and Interpersonal Skills Scale for Adolescents (N=210)

Variables	M	SD	5% Trimmed Mean	Skewness	Kurtosis
PDS	14.44	11.00	13.83	.63	-.19
SES	88.68	13.49	88.18	.80	.70
IPSS	84.39	15.87	84.09	.33	.58

Note. M= Mean, SD= Standard Deviation, PDS= Parental Disharmony Scale, SES= Self-esteem Scale, IPSS= Interpersonal Skills Scale

Table 3

Inter-factor Correlations among Parental Disharmony, Self-Esteem and Interpersonal Skills (N= 210)

Variables	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
1 PD-Total	14.40	10.98	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2 PD-F1	5.09	4.61	.88***	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3 PD-F2	4.67	4.05	.79***	.52***	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4 PD-F3	4.64	4.33	.87***	.67***	.51***	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5 SE-F1	22.98	5.35	-.29***	-.25***	-.26***	-.23**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6 SE-F2	27.90	6.16	-.29**	-.30**	-.18**	-.24***	.43***	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7 SE-F3	28.64	5.13	-.42***	-.40***	-.31***	-.34***	.48***	.51***	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8 3SE	79.43	13.43	-.41***	-.39***	-.31***	-.33***	.78***	.83***	.81***	-	-	-	-	-	-
9 SE-F4	9.25	5.22	.22**	.20**	.21**	.14*	-.24***	-.11	-.11	-.19**	-	-	-	-	-
10 IPS-Total	84.39	15.87	-.38***	-.35***	-.26***	-.36***	.37***	.58***	.49***	.60***	-.08	-	-	-	-
11 IPS-F1	46.98	10.05	-.43***	-.39***	-.32***	-.39***	.46***	.50***	.51***	.61***	-.23**	.86***	-	-	-
12 IPS-F2	24.88	7.13	-.14*	-.14	-.06	-.16*	.10	.40***	.22**	.31***	.16*	.70***	.30***	-	-
13 IPS-F3	12.66	3.69	-.22**	-.23**	-.12	-.21**	.18**	.34***	.30***	.34***	-.03	.63***	.43***	.28***	-

Note. M= Mean, SD= Standard Deviation, 1 PD-Total= Parental Disharmony Total, 2 PD-F1= Lack of Understanding, 3 PD-F2= Financial Issues, 4 PD-F3= Lack of Trust, 5 SE-F1= Academic Self-Esteem, 6 SE-F2= Self-Confidence, 7 SE-F3= Social Self-Esteem, 8 3SE= 3 Self-Esteem Factors Total, 9 SE-F4= Low Self-Esteem, 10 IPS-Total= Interpersonal Skills Total, 11 IPS-F1= Social Engagement, 12 IPS-F2= Sociability, 13 IPS-F3= Social Etiquettes

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Table 4
Linear Regression Analysis Keeping Interpersonal Skills as Dependent Variable (N= 210)

Variables	B	SE	β	95% CI	
				LL	UL
Age	-.53	.74	-.04	-1.98	.92
Gender	4.27	1.8	.14*	.73	7.82
Family System	-1.32	2.03	-.04	-1.99	.92
PD-F1	-.18	.27	-.05	-.71	.34
PD-F2	-.12	.26	-.03	-.64	.39
PD-F3	-.43	.28	-.12	-.99	.13
SE-F1	.21	.19	.07	-.17	.58
SE-F2	1.08	.17	.42***	.76	1.41
SE-F3	.59	.21	.19**	.17	1.01
SE-F4	.20	.18	.07	-.14	.55
R ²	.44				

Note. PD-F1= Lack of Understanding, PD-F2=Financial Issues, PD-F3= Lack of Trust, SE-F1= Academic Self-Esteem, SE-F2= Self-Confidence, SE-F3= Social Self-Esteem, SE-F4= Low Self-Esteem, R²= Coefficient of determination

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

DISCUSSION

The study started by analysing the correlation between parental disharmony, self-esteem, and social skills. Parental disharmony is considered to affect different aspects of the personality of a person, especially during the adolescent period as it is a period of moral and social development at its peak. Many researchers supported the idea that parental disharmony has a negative impact on the self-esteem of teenagers. According to the findings of a study, the self-esteem level of teenagers with parents having conflicted unhealthy relationships was determined to be lower as compared to those living with parents having a healthy marital relationship (Fiaz et al., 2021). Also, another study revealed that parenting stress was linked to lower social skills of adolescents, resulting in a reduction in extracurricular activities (Lee & Joo, 2020). As it was hypothesized that parental disharmony would have a significantly negative association with self-esteem and social skills in adolescents. The results of correlation analysis also revealed that the participants who scored high on the

parental disharmony scale had lower self-esteem and poor interpersonal skills especially, in terms of engaging in social gatherings, as, a study revealed that having parental conflicts at home contributed to self-isolating behaviours leading to low self-esteem of teenagers (Zahra et al., 2023). Similarly, a study on adolescents revealed that those teenagers were more prone to avoid social gatherings whose relationship with their parents was unhealthy because of their mutual conflicts (Suprpto et al., 2023). The findings of another study found a negatively significant relationship between parental disharmony and the social competence of teenagers (Hukkelberg et al., 2019). On the contrary, studies showed that social competence in teenagers reduced the chances of being affected by the parental conflicted relationship due to a strong sense of self within those teenagers (Salavera & Usan, 2021).

The correlation analysis also showed that there was a positive relationship between self-esteem and interpersonal skills. As, a study of meta-analysis revealed that most of the literature focused on the relationship between internalizing social skills and emotional and self-regulatory processes (Salavera et al., 2019). Even the regression analysis showed that self-esteem (adjusted R² = .44) was a positively significant predictor of interpersonal skills.

Also, self-esteem and interpersonal skills are said to have a direct relationship with each other as, a study showed that adolescents with lower self-esteem are prone to have loneliness and rejection sensitivity that makes them socially awkward and they cannot interact with people in social gatherings (Zhou et al., 2020). Furthermore, studies have shown this relationship as a reciprocating effect of both variables. For example; if an individual is not able to interact socially, he would not be able to develop a self-concept which would cause low self-esteem. As, the results of a study implied that the relationship between people's social skills and their self-esteem was truly reciprocal across each stage of development (Harris & Orth, 2020). Individuals with low self-esteem interpret social interactions critically and they may misinterpret social situations, resulting in social issues. Feeling unable to cope with social situations can be extremely unpleasant, especially for adolescents, and can lead to depression symptoms which include isolation and low self-worth. Furthermore, adverse impressions of the outside world may lead to cognitive distortion of self-fulfilling prophecy, resulting in nearly no pleasant interactions (Masselink et al., 2018).

In addition, another hypothesis stated by the literature was that age, gender, family system, parental disharmony, and self-esteem would be significant predictors of interpersonal skills. The results revealed that age, family system, and factors of parental disharmony were not significant predictors of interpersonal skills. Only, gender and self-esteem predicted interpersonal skills positively as mentioned earlier. The prediction of gender was specifically linked with females. However, recent research on adolescents and their social development revealed that girls showed more social skills as compared to boys (Smith & Kerpelman, 2022). These results show that teenage girls are more prone to have good interpersonal skills including socializing and practicing social etiquette. All these results were observed in the cultural context as, explained by the cultural literature that, girls of collectivistic culture are usually demanded to behave according to the social gatherings and expected to interact with people at family gatherings, it apparently makes

them good at social interaction despite of the inner feelings. These findings were also consistent with earlier research indicating that girls have better levels of collaboration, intrapersonal, and interpersonal skills than boys (Salavera, Usan & Jarie, 2018). Another systematic review showed that females had more interpersonal skills as compared to boys because they got to engage in family events more than the boys who are not required to engage in the talking session (Morowatisharifabad et al., 2019). Similarly, in Pakistan, collectivism prevails, therefore, gender disparities are the most common thing observed in any phenomenon. Therefore, social skills are also determined by the females of the house because, in collectivistic cultures, mothers were observed to be more concerned with their child's social abilities to have healthy interactions with family and friends (Zahra & Saleem, 2021).

The intriguing results for predicting interpersonal skills showed self-esteem as a positive predictor as per the suggestions of literature which stated that it would be positively associated with interpersonal skills, meaning that more self-esteem would lead to having good interpersonal skills and vice versa (Cameron & Granger, 2019). Researches have revealed that having a positive self-image oneself leads to having a good social image eventually making social interactions easier (Rice & Dolgin, 2005 as cited by Katsantonis et al., 2023). Also, another important factor for the self-esteem scale was academic self-esteem, which had a positive relationship with the social competence of students in higher secondary student (Coleman, 2022). Similar results were observed in an experimental study where teenage participants were taught to have social etiquette. The findings indicated an increase in their self-esteem (Orth & Robins, 2022). The reason for the partial rejection of the hypothesis stated above could be due to the presence of other cultural factors like family type, social norms, and values and non-cultural factors like interpersonal conflicts, and conflicted body-mind relationships (Shujja & Malik, 2011). As, age, family system, and factors of parental disharmony did not predict interpersonal skills, that means the current study includes participants from nuclear families, that are not

very individual or independent from the rest of the family, and the extended family members still have an influence over the decisions of such families. According to the local researches, interpersonal skills were formed majorly by the culture and culture was dependent on the family system (Zahra et al., 2020). Therefore, more participants belonging to nuclear families might be the reason that the family system could not predict interpersonal skills, as, there is apparently no difference between nuclear and joint families because every family has collectivistic values in the form of involvement from extended family members on traditional events (Collins et al., 2020).

In addition, age showed no association with interpersonal skills as, a culturally relevant study also found no variation in interpersonal abilities during early, middle, and late teenage years (Salavera, Usan & Jarie, 2020). In the Pakistani cultural settings, childhood is somewhat prolonged, and youngsters remain under their parental shadow for a longer length of time while making crucial life decisions, as a result, the manifestation of interpersonal skills remains consistent throughout the adolescence period (Saleem et al., 2019). Furthermore, parental disharmony along with its factors, did not predict interpersonal skills in the current study results, because of the predictable presence of resilience and optimistic thinking as the same research as above showed that teenagers tend to show good interpersonal skills, even with parental conflicts because they have resilience to cope with the distress arising from parental conflicts (Saleem et al., 2019). A lot of studies focused on the emotional factors into consideration while determining social competence instead of the age of the individuals (Diener et al., 2018). Similarly, a study debated that adolescence is a period ranging from 13-19 years of age, and with increasing age, the scores of social skills remained the same because of the fact that age alone would not increase social competence but individual experiences and responses definitely affected social skills (Penalva et al., 2020). Hence, the discussion validated all the results of the current research. As the correlational analysis showed that parental disharmony was negatively associated with self-esteem and interpersonal skills indicating that individuals having parental

disharmony within their homes would be more likely to have low self-esteem and poor social skills. In addition, female teenagers were likely to have good interpersonal skills as compared to boys because of cultural expectations of a collectivistic culture.

CONCLUSION

This study offered a ground-breaking exploration of the impact of parental disharmony, self-esteem, and social skills on adolescents within the collectivistic cultural framework of Pakistan. Although these concepts are universally recognized, their expression and influence differ across cultural contexts. The primary goal was to investigate how parental disharmony detrimentally affects teenagers' self-esteem and social skills, and to understand the interconnection between self-esteem and social skills.

The results clearly demonstrated that parental disharmony significantly undermines both self-esteem and social skills. Furthermore, a strong positive link was found between self-esteem and social skills, highlighting the vital role these factors play in adolescent development. Also, regression analysis revealed that only female gender, along with academic and social self-esteem, significantly predicted interpersonal skills in adolescents and age is just a number because experiences can be gained at an early age as well.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE SUGGESTIONS

- The information was gathered merely from an urbanized sample of adolescents from public sector schools, which might restrict the phenomenon's ability to be generalized. Therefore, future studies should concentrate on including a broader age range of subcultural samples as well.
- Self-report measures were used to assess the phenomenon that might have little opportunity for diversity in choices. In the future, other data collection procedures that are more feasible and have fewer odds of participant response bias should also be used.
- A cross-sectional research design was adopted in this study which is why, future researchers should employ a longitudinal research design to study the impact of parental disharmony on self-esteem and interpersonal skills over different time periods.

- As the data was collected in front of the teachers and other students, the results might have been affected by the presence of biases or fear of judgment. Therefore, other methods of data collection should be used to ensure the validity of the data.

Author's Note

The study was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the Ethical Committee, Department of Clinical Psychology, School of Professional Psychology, University of Management and Technology (UMT), Lahore. Verbal informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection. A part of this study was presented online at the 11th International Zeugma Conference on Scientific Research, held in Gaziantep, Turkey. Additionally, part of the study was presented as a poster presentation at the 7th International Conference on Mental Health, Well-being, and Happiness: A Way Forward. The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest to disclose. All correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Ms. Arfa Javed, Lecturer, Department of Clinical Psychology, School of Professional Psychology, University of Management and Technology (UMT), Lahore.

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